

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1985	Terje Lohndal	2004	2012			Norwegian linguist	
1985	Tereza Kuldová	2006	2013		w	Czech social anthropologist and fashion curator, specializing on contemporary India and biker subculture in Europe	
1985	Fitor Ollomani	2007	2015			Albanian assistant of Professor in linguistics	
1985	Jenny L. Davis	2008	2012		w	American Native Assistant Professor of Anthropology, American Indian Studies, and Gender & Women's Studies	
1985	André de Oliveira Leitão	2008	No			Portuguese Doctoral researcher at Centre of Religious History	
1985	Luisa Garcia Manso	2009	2013		w	Spanish Assistant Professor Hispanic Contemporary Literature	
1985	Raúl Zecca Castel	2009	No			Italian anthropologist, documentary filmmaker and translator	
1985	Artea Panajotović	2009	2017		w	Serbian Assistant Professor, Faculty of Foreign Languages	
1985	Ángel Narro	2010	2013			Spanish Ancient Greek Professor. Researcher on Greek and Byzantine literature	
1985	Anna Endresen	2010	2015		w	Swedish linguist	
1985	Kristina Jõekalda	2010			w	Estonian Junior Research Fellow, Institute of Art History and Visual Culture	
1985	Hrayr Khanjian	2011	2013			American linguist	
1985	Amadeu Corbera Jaume	2011	2019			Spanish Head of Department of Musicology and Music Education	
1985	Филиппенко Валерия Викторовна	2011	2015		w	Belarusian cultural scientist	
1985	I Gedé Gita Purnama	2012	No			Indonesian lecturer in Balinese Language and Literature	
1985	Kenan Saatcioglu	2012	2017			Turkish assistant Professor of Suleyman Demirel University Faculty of Fine Arts, Textile and Fashion Design Department	
1985	Knut Melvær	2012	No			Norwegian humanities technologist of Department of Archeology, History, Cultural Studies and Religion	

1985	Tia-Simone Gardner	2013	No	w	American Doctoral Candidate, Gender Women's and Sexuality Studies
1985	Shahram Shahryari	2013	2017		Indian Experienced Adjunct Lecturer
1985	Beri Hussein	2013	No		Iragi Kurdish linguist
1985	Rebin Abdulqader Azeez	2013			Iraqi Kurdish Lecturer of Applied Linguistics
1985	Ahmed Aiyad Gaibani	2014	No		Lybian English Language Lecturer (Applied Linguistics)
1985	Simon Gonzalez	2014	2015		Venezuelan Postdoctoral Fellow, Centre of Excellence for the Dynamics of Language
1985	Julie Ndwiga	2014	No	w	Kenyan Gender Advisor at RTI International
1985	Kristina Koppel	2015	No	w	Estonian Early-stage researcher of Institute of Estonian and General Linguistics
1985	Parinaz Faghihi	2015	No	w	Iranian PhD student in Art and Design, Faculty of Fine Arts
1985	Lynn Eekhof	2015	No	w	Dutch PhD-student in the Narrative Cognition and Communication
1985	Mārtiņš Laizāns	2017	No		Latvian researcher in Literature
1985	Rawshan E Fatima	2017	No	w	Bangladeshi Doctoral Student at Department of Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies
1985	Gül Musaoğlu	2017	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1985	Oguz Can OK	2018	No		Turkish PhD Student in Gender Studies
1986	Jiří Milička	2007	2016		Czech linguist
1986	Martin Paul Eve	2007	2013		British academic and writer
1986	João Leal	2007			Portuguese Professor of Lighting, Cinematography, Applied Photography and Phototography
1986	Ayşegül Demir	2008	2017	w	Turkish linguist and literature critic
1986	Jelena Pavličić	2008	2016	w	Serbian Art historian
1986	Maria Morozova	2008	2013	w	Russian Senior Researcher, Institute for Linguistic Studies
1986	Madara Eversone	2008	No	w	Latvian Researcher; Institute of Literature (literary studies, soviet studies soviet history, cultural studies)
1986	Anke Himmelreich (née Assmann)	2009	2017	w	German linguist
1986	Byron Fong	2009	No		American PhD student of Graduate Program in Visual and Cultural Studies

1986 Sara Librenjak	2009	No	w	Croatian Master of Linguistics and Information Science, Japanologist
1986 Katy Barrett	2010	2013	w	British Curator of Art Collections at the Science Museum (intersections between histories of art and science)
1986 Maja Pandžić	2010	2015	w	Croatian Professor of Russian literature and literary theory (feminist literary criticism, literary theory, spatial theory, film and theater)
1986 Andrea Deme	2010	2015	w	Hungarian speech scientist
1986 Emilia Quiñones-Otal	2010	2014	w	Puerto Rican Associate Professor of Art History
1986 Anwar Masduki	2010			Indonesian editorial Board of Theology and Religious Studies
1986 Adi Maslo	2011	2016		Bosnian Professor of Linguistics
1986 Marian Weger	2011	No		German audio visual artist, musician and sound engineer
1986 Bakk Ágnes Karolina	2011	No	w	Hungarian Lecturer in VR-narratives and immersive storytelling
1986 Nicole N. Conti	2011	No	w	American Doctoral Candidate, Department of Art History
1986 Jundan Jasmine Zhang	2011	2016	w	Chinese Postdoctoral researcher of Department of historical, philosophical and religious studies
1986 Dickens Leonard	2012	2017		Indian researcher of Comparative Literature Department (Film and Culture studies, religion, critical pedagogy)
1986 Ali Hürriyetoğlu	2012	2016		Turkish Postdoctoral Researcher in computational Linguistics
1986 Rachel Devorah Rome	2012	2018	w	American sonic artist and feminist
1986 George C. Nche	2012			Nigerian Lecturer of Department of Religion & Cultural Studies
1986 Dr Hleze Kunju	2013	2017		South African Lecturer, Creative Writing of School of Languages & Literatures (African Languages), musician
1986 Kemi Adeyemi	2013	2016	w	Nigerian Assistant Professor of Gender, Women and Sexuality Studies

1986	Tami Coelho Ocar	2013	No	w	Brazilian PhD researcher, Master in History, in the area of Cultural History
1986	Seyyed Mohammad Bagher Borghei Modarres	2014	2014		Iranian linguist, critic, cineast and religious scholar
1986	Isuru Dharmarathna	2014	No	w	Sri Lankan Lecturer (Probationary) in Speech and Language Therapy
1986	Shyama Ramsamy	2014	2019	w	Indian Teacher of English Language, French and Literature
1986	Katarzyna Kułakowska	2015	2017	w	Polish Adjunct of Institute of Art (Feminist Sociology, Microhistory, and Memoir and Autobiography)
1986	Diaa Ahmed Mohamed Ahmedi	2015	2017		Egyptian artist, educator, researcher, and creator
1986	Sadek Kessous	2015	2017		British Early Career Teaching and Research Fellow (English Literature)
1986	Didem Bilen	2015	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1986	Aqleem Fatimah	2017	No	w	Pakistani Lecturer Gender and Women Studies
1986	Camilo Sol Inti Soler Caicedo	2017	No		Colombian anthropologist and researcher in Dance and popular culture
1986	Rusul Adnan N. Al Asadi	2018	No	w	Iraqi Assistant Lecturer of Department of English
1986	Peter Folan, S.J.	2019			American doctoral candidate in the theology department
1987	Jason Zentz	2007	2016		American linguist, Assistant Dean for Academic and Faculty Affairs in the Faculty of Arts and Sciences
1987	Nilufar Abdurakhmonova	2007	2018	w	Uzbeki Senior teacher of the department of Information and modern pedagogical technologies in Tashkent state university of Uzbek language and literature
1987	Евгений Хамидов	2007	2012		Russian Lecturer in department of Religion Studies
1987	Sándor Trippó	2010	2019		Hungarian cultural and media studies scholar
1987	Christoph Hesse	2010	2015		British researcher in Linguistics & English Language
1987	Amber Case	2011		w	American cyborg anthropologist, user experience designer and public speaker (interaction between humans and technology)
1987	Martina Podboj	2011	No	w	Croatian researcher in Linguistics, Languages and Linguistics, and Critical Discourse Analysis

1987	Antje Stoehr	2012	2015	w	Dutch Postdoctoral Researcher of Basque Center on Cognition, Brain and Language
1987	Kazuhiro Okada	2012	2015	w	Japanese Specially-Appointed Assistant Professor (Japanese Linguistics, Writing Systems)
1987	Areen Ahmed Muhammed	2013	No		Iraqi Assistant Instructor In English Language and Linguistics
1987	Ayşenur Ceren Asmaz	2013	2018	w	Turkish Assistant Professor of Plastic Arts
1987	Ahmet Erdost Yastibaş	2013	No		Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1987	Peter Mano	2013	No		Slovakian Anthropology graduate student
1987	Péter Jeszenszky	2014	2018		Hungarian Postdoctoral Researcher (Center for the Study of Language in Society)
1987	Viola Kazanina	2014	No	w	Belarusian art historian
1987	Azroz Mohd	2014	No		Malaysian Arts and Culture Strategist who is currently full time lecturer for the Film, Theatre and Animation (FiTA) program
1987	Бульгина Екатерина Викторовна	2015	2019	w	Russian Lecturer of Institute of the Russian Language and Culture
1987	Ebru Uğur	2015	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1987	Shafi Md. Mostofa	2015			Bangladeshi Assistant Professor, World Religions and Culture
1987	Asante Lucy Mtenje	2016	2016	w	Malawian Lecturer of English Literature (poet, short fiction writer, visual artist and literary scholar)
1987	Emir Mejremić	2016	No		Bosnian PhD Student in Transdisciplinary Studies of Contemporary Art and Media
1987	Maziar Rezai	2017	No		Iranian Design-Activist, Design Researcher and Film Critic
1988	Sandra Folie	2010	2019	w	Austrian lecturer at the Department of Comparative Literature (comparative and world, women's fiction, gender studies, intersectionality)
1988	Иван Полторацкий	2012	No		Russian Assistant of the Department of History and Theory of Literature
1988	Nina Ditmajer	2012	2019	w	Slovenian Theologist, Linguist, Literary Historian
1988	Fahreta Fijuljanin	2013	No	w	Bosnian Senior Teaching Assistant of Language and Literature
1988	Kobie van Krieken	2013	2016	w	Dutch Researcher at the Centre for Language Studies

1988 Polina Drozdova	2013	2018	w	Dutch researcher of Centre for Language Studies
1988 Fekete Tamás	2013	No		Hungarian assistant lecturer of Department of English Linguistics
1988 Artis Ostups	2013	No		Latvian poet, translator and essayist
1988 Pranvera Osmani	2013	No	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian language
1988 Aseel Zibin	2014	2017	w	Jordanian Assistant Professor of Linguistics
1988 Jonas Berthod	2014	No		Swiss art historian (Critical History of Graphic Design)
1988 Biljana Lazić	2014	No	w	Serbian PhD candidate in Faculty of Philology
1988 Şeyda Yağmur Balcı	2014	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1988 Aleksandar Feodorov	2015	2017		Bulgarian Fulbright Scholar, Assistant Professor of Institute for Literature
1988 Mohammed R. H. Qwaider	2016	No		Palestinean Computational scientist in Human Language
1988 Joseph H Herrera	2016	2016		American Instructor in the Department of Critical Culture, Gender and Race Studies
1988 Jasna Bićanić	2018	No	w	Croatian Associate for coordination, student mobility and quality assurance of postgraduate study. Faculty of humanities and social sciences
1989 Edgar Mauricio Ulloa Molina	2009	2016		Costa Rican Professor of Art History
1989 Prima Vidya Asteria	2011	No	w	Indonesian Lecturer of Indonesian Language and Literature Education
1989 Fabiana Micaele da Silva	2011	No	w	Brazilian Master in Scientific and Cultural Dissemination by the Laboratory of Scientific Journalism
1989 Abd. Aziz Faiz	2011	No		Indonesian Lecturer Sociology of Religion
1989 Nikolaos Tsitsoulis	2013	No		Greek Business Development Manager at OTA Insight
1989 Müge Umaç	2013	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1989 Eleanor Chodroff	2014	2017	w	American Lecturer in Phonetics and Phonology
1989 Ludivine Crible	2014	2017	w	Belgian linguist
1989 Songkran Somchandra	2014	No		Thai Lecturer, Department of Music and Performing Arts
1989 Benny Lewis	2014	No		Irish author, polyglot, and blogger who defines himself as a "technomad language hacker"
1989 Irina Masnikosa	2014	No	w	Croatian PhD student in Linguistics

1989 Catalina Popa	2016 No	w	Romanian researcher of Flute, singer
1989 Josly van Wyk	2016 No	w	South African Research assistant in Fine Arts
1989 Veronica Lion	2017 No	w	Israeli Phd candidate in Gender Studies
1989 Reshma Ramesh	2017	w	Indian Research Scholar, Centre for Women's empowerment and Gender Equality
1989 Yeliz Turan Yunusođlu	2018 No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1989 Nadine Mund	2018 2018	w	Austrian assistant professor of Religion
1989 Tuđçenur Kavgacı	2019 No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages